

EFFECT OF PLY THICKNESS AND TEMPERATURE ON TRANSVERSE CRACKING PROCESS IN COMPOSITE LAMINATES

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ABSTRACT

The development of cryogenic tanks in composite materials is one the principal approach of space industry to reduce the manufacturing and launch cost of the rocket. To satisfy both the strength and permeability requirements, design of linerless tanks requires the study of the relationship between damage and permeability. This paper presents a part of the characterization of cracking process in the composite laminate. An experimental method is introduced based on the observation of the microstructure under tensile loading from the low to ambient temperature. The material is a cross-ply laminate with both intermediate (150 g/m²) and low (75 g/m²) fibre mass plies. Experimental analysis are supported thanks to a numerical model based on cohesive element, which represent the transverse cracks. Results highlight the impact of both low temperature and ply thickness on initiation and growth of transverse cracking.

1 INTRODUCTION

The cryogenic tanks allow the storage of liquid propellant for motor provision such as liquid hydrogen (20K) or liquid methane (110K). These tanks take a large part of the total volume of launchers. Today and for many cases, cryogenic vessels are manufactured with metallic materials and mass criteria are therefore critical in technical specifications. A solution is to develop composite cryogenic tanks with a liner which ensure permeability requirement. The presence of composite thus contain the effort of pressurization. This solution is already employed for small size tanks like the sphere for helium pressurization (4K). Nowadays, skills limit in manufacturing of metallic materials and the small pressure in cryogenic tanks lead to sizing thick liner with thickness close to metallic tanks. Because of this, space industry challenge is to manufacture composite tanks without any liner. Composite part would thus ensure both the resistance and permeability requirements. The type of cryogenic fluid stored coupled with the pressurization strength induce a high thermomechanical loading to the material. These researches are focused on characterizing the impact of these types of loading on transverse cracking process in composite laminates. Under thermal and mechanical loading, even far from failure resistance, we could observed the appearance and the development of damage mechanisms [1]. These mechanisms are mainly transverse crack and micro delamination. During the application of the load, the damage in each plies progress and coalesces with each other. Therefore, a crack network is created (Figure 1) and when there is continuity between exterior and interior of the tank wall, the crack network become a leak path and the tank permeability decreases quickly [2], [3]. Many geometric parameters rule the creation and development of matrix cracking such as orientation, number and thickness of plies [4], [5]. Reduction of ply thickness increases the cracking threshold. Hence, the thin ply technology is an interesting approach to grow back the first leak path appearance.

The global strategy of these works aims to characterize the relation between damage and permeability in composite laminates on temperature of the industrial application in order to build, enrich and validate a model at mesoscopic scale that predict the leak path according to the loading applied on the structure [3], [6]. This strategy is based upon experimental (microscopic observations and tomography under load) and virtual testing, which allows the characterization of crack network development in the composite laminate and then building the meso-model. The validation of the model is mainly based on leak path measures on tubular specimen in composite under pressure [7].

This paper presents a part of the experimental and numerical characterisation needed to build the meso-model. The first section describes the experimental method developed to characterise the material damage under uniaxial loading from ambient temperature to -130°C . The complexity and the heaviness of the experimental protocol encourage the researchers to develop virtual testing in order to complete experimental observations [8]. The second section describes the discrete modelling, based on cohesive zone model, proposed to simulate the damage scenario at mesoscopic scale (transverse crack and microdelamination). Finally, the experimental results are presented and correlated in order to validate the global approach to characterize the damage mechanisms of a composite laminate under thermal and mechanical loading.

Figure 1 - Cracks network for three damaged plies, which lead to a leak path, drawing and micrography

2 EXPERIMENTAL CHARACTERIZATION

2.1 Test presentation

The studied material is a composite laminate with long carbon fibre and epoxy matrix. The size of the specimens is $230 \times 25 \text{ mm}^2$ (length x wide) and there is a tab of 40mm length on the extremity. The specimens come from a plate of $300 \times 300 \text{ mm}^2$ manufactured by automated fibre placement (AFP). The stacking sequences studied are cross ply laminate with two different fibre masses for having the possibility to observe the effect of thickness ply. The first sequence, $[0/90/0/90/0/90/0_{0.5}]_s$ (13 plies), are manufactured with low fibre mass (75 g/m^2) and the second one, $[0/90/0/90_2]_s$ (7 plies), with intermediate fibre mass (150 g/m^2). Tests are performed at three temperatures (20°C , -80°C and -130°C) in an environmental room (Figure 2). The room is monitored through a thermocouple type T placed on the specimen. The mechanical loading is ensured by a tensile device with a capacity of 100kN. The loading is controlled by strain and the observations of the cracks are performed at ambient temperature at different strain plateaus. Previously, one side of the specimens are polished to allow microscopic observations.

The specimen is stabilized at the target temperature then the mechanical loading is applied to the strain ϵ_{max} , which allows the initiation or the propagation of the damage. The strain is then reduced and maintained at 80% of the maximal strain in order to limit the effect of viscous phenomenon and to avoid the evolution of the damage during the microscopic observations. Then we move back up the specimen

at 20°C to ease the observation. The inspection involve to quantify the number of transverse cracks and their position on an observation length (80mm). A sufficient length is needed to evaluate the statistical effects relatively to the variability of the material. When the control is done, the temperature is cool down again to the test temperature and then the specimen is loaded to the next strain plateaus higher than the previously. The operation is iterated for an enough number of stage, which allow us to draw the evolution of the reduce transverse crack rate (Eq. 1) according to the longitudinal strain applied on the laminate.

$$\bar{\rho} = \frac{N_f^{90^\circ}}{L_{obs}} h^{90^\circ} \quad (1)$$

With $\bar{\rho}$ the reduce cracking rate (unseized) [-], $N_f^{90^\circ}$ the number of transverse cracks in the 90° ply considered [-], L_{obs} the observation length [mm] and h^{90° the thickness ply [mm].

Figure 2 - Illustration of experimental device which allow the observation of laminate microstructure under loading

2.2 Effect of thickness ply

The Figure 3 illustrates the effect of thickness ply on transverse cracking process according to longitudinal mechanical strain apply on the laminates. For the three laminates, we observe a first phase during which one the cracking process increase slowly. This slow onset is probably a consequence of an initial flaw in the material (porosity, micro crack, matrix cluster, etc.), which pilots the appearance of the first transverse cracks. In fact, it is necessary to make a control on a sufficient observation length in order to get these effects of variability. When the loading increases, the distribution of the transverse crack becomes more homogeneous and the evolution of the cracking rate move up quickly and almost linear. We can make out a third phase on the curve of the thick ply (573 μ m) of the laminates [0/90/0/90₂]_s. This latter phase matches with the damage saturation, which occurs when the transverse ply considered is enough unload. In addition, we can observe that the damage threshold increase when the thickness ply decreases. It is coherent with the fact that the damage threshold of thick ply is piloted by a stress criterion while the cracking process of the intermediate and thin plies is piloted by an energy criterion [9]. Overall, the ply thickness affects the damage threshold so the first appearance of transverse

cracks. In addition, the cracking rate is lower during loading and before failure. Pushing the cracking threshold is a very interesting criterion for permeability problems.

Figure 3 - Evolution of reduce crack rate according to longitudinal stress laminate

2.3 Temperature effect

In addition, the Figure 3 displays the effect of the temperature on transverse cracking process according to longitudinal mechanical strain apply on the laminates. The stratification of the simple ply studied is $[0/90/0/90_2]_s$. Its thickness being intermediate, it is difficult to capture the saturation of the damage. On the other hand, two phases are observed for each of the curves. A first in which the transverse cracks appear slowly and a second where the damage progresses more quickly and with a more homogeneous distribution until rupture of the specimen. The threshold of initiation of the damage does not seem to be affected by the decrease of the temperature. On the other hand, the rate of transverse cracks increases quicker at -80°C and -130°C for both damage phases. The kinetics of cracking is therefore faster at low temperatures. The rate of cracks recorded before rupture of the test specimen is greater when the temperature decreases. These observations can be explained by the fact that the resin stiffens at low temperatures, becomes more brittle and its breaking energy decreases [10], [11]. Also, the breaking strain of the laminate decreases with temperature. This can result from damage to the folds at 0° caused by the transverse stresses induced by the Poisson effect and the thermal expansions. As a result, we can observe that the decrease in temperature tends to reduce the gap between the crack threshold and the rupture of the laminate.

3 NUMERICAL MODELLING

3.1 General strategy

The amount of information required to build and identify a predictive model at the mesoscopic scale and the complexity of the experimental protocol encourage us to develop the virtual testing. This method allows completing the characterization of the damage and the interaction effects in a composite laminate

under thermal and mechanical loading. The overall idea is to reproduce all the damage scenarios under in-plane loading on any stacking sequence. Then, we will be able to identify the parameters which governing these scenarios (transverse crack rate, crossover rate, etc.) and enrich the meso-model of damage.

3.2 The numerical model

The modelling is made on the software of numerical calculation ABAQUS. We use the method of cohesive zone model to simulate by a discrete way the initiation and propagation of damage [12]. In this paper, the study is focalised on transverse cracks in the ply loading transversally.

In this first study, delaminates are modelled by an undamaged cohesive behaviour with the same stiffness than transverse crack. The use of cohesive zone model needs to assume the localisation of the future transverse cracks. This method consists to define an interaction between two surfaces which depend of many parameters. Figure 4 illustrates the behaviour of mixed mode cohesive zone. The first parameter allow to introduce an initial stiffness in the cohesive zone which is the relative displacement of the surfaces according to the strain. An initiation strain criterion of quadratic type is defined (Eq. 2). The damage evolution is ruled by an energetic criterion with linear softening (Eq. 3). The Benzeggagh-Kenane criterion is used and allow taking care the mixed modes for composite materials.

$$\left(\frac{\langle\sigma_n\rangle}{\sigma_n^0}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\langle\sigma_s\rangle}{\sigma_s^0}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\langle\sigma_t\rangle}{\sigma_t^0}\right)^2 = 1 \quad (2)$$

$$G^c = G_n^c + (G_s^c - G_n^c) \left(\frac{G_s}{G_n + G_s}\right)^\eta \quad (3)$$

With G_n the cracking energy for mode I, $G_s = G_s + G_t$ the cracking energy for mode II and G^c the overall critical energy release rate.

Figure 4 - Illustration of a mixed mode response in a cohesive zone

The model is a representation of the laminates on 80mm of length. This length is the same as which one observed experimentally. Many of cohesive zone are modelled to represent the potential future transverse cracks. The number of cohesive zone chosen and modelled is higher than the number of transverse cracks observed experimentally at the saturation point or before the laminate failure. The zone cohesive stiffness must be sufficient to not modify the laminate stiffness. The cell could be submit to a thermal loading by introducing a temperature variation at each nodes of the model. The mechanical loading is uniaxial. We clamp one of the extremity and the other one is submitted to a displacement.

The complexity is in the description of the progressivity of transverse crack phenomenon that is piloted by the initial state of the material ad especially by the presence of defects. Usually, these statistical effects are modelled with a probabilistic approach [4, 9]. The variability are generally presented as a defects that tends to decrease the local properties of the material. We choose an asymmetric Weibull distribution (Eq. 4). For this study, we implement the distribution on the initiation normal strain. We choose to not affect some variability on cracking energy because, in practice, each transverse cracks appear instantaneously on the whole thickness of the layup and on an sufficient length. Consequently, the energy value and the effects of the variability present in the microstructure are averaged.

$$P(\sigma) = 1 - \exp\left(\left[-\frac{\sigma - \sigma_{th}}{\sigma_0}\right]^k\right) \quad (4)$$

With $P(\sigma)$ the function of repartition or the cumulate probability, σ_{th} the strain of cracking initiation, σ_0 and k a constant to define.

3.3 Identification and results

The identification of the parameters that affect the cohesive behavior of damage modelling is achieved in many steps. First, a simple crack cell is simulated (Figure 5). It allow to define the stiffness K and the numerical viscosity of the cohesive law in order to have a good representation of the transverse cracking process. Experimentally, we can observe that the transverse crack appear instantaneously et on the entire ply thickness.

In a second part, we simulate a cross ply laminate with many cracks modelled by cohesive zones (Figure 6). Edge effects are not taken into account because it is not an influential phenomenon for the considered laminate. The cell is modelled in 2D with only one volumetric element in the width. The experimental stress raised at cracking initiation on a thick ply allow us, because of laminate theory, to determine the associated strain. The foot of the chosen distribution has a probability close to zero. It has not physic sense to directly associate the foot of the distribution to the strain σ_{th} (Eq. 4). Because of this, we choose to define our probabilistic law to have an initiation strain at 1% of probability. Finally, we define the two other parameters σ_0 and k in order to describe as well as possible the progressivity of the cracking process. The values of cracking energy G_n^c and G_S^c come from the literature [13].

Figure 7 present the first results obtained with the model. In order to observe the model answer for a cracking piloted by a strain criterion and an energy criterion, we made the study on many plies thickness which are the same studied experimentally. The experimental results are issued from the experimental characterization presented in the previous section. For the same set of cohesive law parameters and properties distribution, the model tends to have a good representation of the thickness ply effect. In fact, it delays the cracking threshold as the ply thickness decreases. The implemented distribution allows to find again the experimental observation and especially the process progressivity for each ply thickness. The damage saturation for the thick ply is also described as experimentally. The results of the intermediate thickness ply present a progressive initiation but the cracking threshold is pushed up and the transverse crack evolution increase quicker than experimentally. The numerical draw of the thin ply describe a damage initiation lightly displaced but as progressive as experimental cracking evolution.

Figure 5 - Modelling of elementary cell with one crack

Figure 6 - Modelling of cross-ply laminate with multi-cracks

4 CONCLUSIONS

This paper presents a paired method with experimental and numerical characterization, which allows observing and describing the initiation and evolution of transverse crack in a cross ply composite laminate for ambient temperature to -130°C. The experimental study is realised on two specimen with different stacking sequences and fibre mass, which allows illustrating the thickness effect in the cracking process. The observations indicate that the thin ply push up the cracking threshold and the transverse crack rate during loading and before the laminate failure. The temperature effect is also observed with experimental tests carried out at low temperatures. We observed that the reduction of the temperature has no significant influence on the cracking threshold. On the other hand, it produces a quicker damage kinetic with higher transverse crack rate. The diminution of ply thickness paired to a low temperature lead to reduce significantly the gap between the cracking initiation and the material failure. For tank sizing point of view, it is a really interesting observations because it must ensure both permeability and resistance requirement. Finally, a numerical model based on cohesive zone method is presented. The modelling is confronted with experimental results led from ambient to low temperature and for three plies thickness. The model tends to predict a good description of the cracking evolution during loading. The cracking threshold and the progressive aspect of damage process is correctly represented. The saturation of damage raised experimentally on the thick ply is also described. Because of this, it seems that the identification methodology chosen to determine the parameter of the cohesive law is relevant. This first results will have to be confirmed with a sensibility study on the parameters of the probabilistic parameters. An additional confrontation with some other experimental results will be necessary and especially with cracking test carry out at low temperatures.

Figure 7 - Confrontation of numerical modelling with experimental tests at ambient temperature

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